

Feasibility Studies on the Preparation of Butter and Ghee

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Abstract

In this research work, feasibility studies were made on the preparation of butter and ghee. Milk samples from different farms were collected. Cow milks from Friesian and Native Cow were used as raw materials. Similarly, buffalo milks from River Breed and Swamp Breed were also used as raw materials. Firstly, butter was prepared from pasteurized cream by natural souring (Traditional Method). Moreover, butter was prepared by using mother culture. Sample culture was used to prepare mother culture. The effect of amount of mother culture for the required pH of milk cream during 16hr was studied. It was found that (6 g) of mother culture is suitable for (100 g) of cow milk cream and (9 g) of mother culture is suitable for (100 g) of buffalo milk cream. Yield percentage, physical and chemical properties of prepared butters were also studied and compared. It was observed that the butters prepared by using mother culture have sweet butter smell and their yield percentages are higher than that of butters prepared by natural souring. Secondly, ghee was prepared from milk cream and creamery butter. Yield percentage of prepared ghee was studied and the physical and chemical properties of prepared ghee were determined. It was also found that yield percentage of ghee prepared from milk cream is 50% (w/w) and that of ghee prepared from creamery butter is 80 % (w/w). It was also examined that the quality of ghee prepared from cow milk cream is the best among these samples.

Key words: milk, butter, ghee

Introduction

Milk and milk products have formed an important part of the diet of man. All mammals produce milk after the birth of the young and man has used the milk of many animals for his own food. The cow is, of course, the most important of all these animals as a supplier of food for man, but reindeer, buffalo or goat milk is more important in some parts of the world (Eckles, 1982).

More than five percent of the world's milk comes from buffalo. Buffalo milk is used in much the same way as cow milk. It is high in fats and total solid, which gives it a right flavor. Many people prefer it to cow milk and are willing to pay more for it (Winton, 2000).

The milk from cows and buffaloes will vary in composition and many other factors. These include the breed, individuality of the animal, age, stage of lactation, season of the year, the feed, time of milking, period of time between milking, the physiologic condition of the cow whether it is calm or excited, whether it is receiving drugs and so on (Eckles, 1982). Milk is also an excellent medium for the growth of many bacteria. Thus, it could easily be spoiled. The low acidity and high nutrient content of milk make it the perfect breeding ground for bacteria including those that cause food poisoning (Salle, 1979).

Due to perishable nature of milk, some form of processing is necessary to extend its shelf-life, transform it into different products to expand its market and to generate income by adding value. Ordinary heat treatment or pasteurization, while destroying harmful bacteria, does not make milk absolutely free from spoilage organism. In a tropical climate, milk becomes unfit for human consumption within a day or two (Food Cycle, 1994).

Processing milk into a dairy product makes it more stable for storage over extended period of time. In the tropics where ambient temperature are high and refrigeration is not readily available, milk may be concentrated by boiling or made into butter or ghee or other products which keep better at room temperatures. When there is an abundant local supply, storage and marketing may have a low priority, leading to wastage. Processing helps eliminate wastage and also adds value (Food Cycle, 1994).

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Materials and Methods

Preparation of Butter

Preparation of Butter by Natural Souring

The cream was separated from milk samples (cow milk and buffalo milk) by using cream separator. The yield percentages of cream and skim milk from different milk samples are shown in Table 1.

Then, 100 g of cream was pasteurized at 82 °C for 30 sec to destroy germ satisfactorily and inactivate enzyme. After pasteurization, the cream was stored at room temperature until enough was obtained to make into butter. Cream stored in this way was acidified automatically after which it was churned. The butter milk was poured off. The same amount of cold water as the amount of butter milk which had been removed was added and the mixture was churned. Water was drawn off and butter was removed, packed and stored in the refrigerator.

Yield percentages of prepared butters are recorded in Table 2.

Preparation of Butter by Using Mother Culture

The cream was separated from milk samples (cow milk and buffalo milk) by using cream separator. The yield percentage of cream and skim milk are shown in Table 1.

Then, 100 g of cream was pasteurized at 82 °C for 30 sec and cooled to 21 °C. This was followed by the addition of mother culture (4-10%) and let to stand at 21°C for 16 h for gradual ripening. When it reached the required acidity and pH of 4.7, it was ready to churn for butter making. After that, fermented cream was churned and the butter milk was poured off. The same amount of cold water as the amount of butter milk which has been removed was added and the mixture was churned. Water was drawn off and butter was removed. Finally, the butter was placed in a sterilized container and stored in the refrigerator.

The yield percentages of prepared cultured butters are shown in Table 5.

Preparation of Ghee

Preparation of Ghee from Milk Cream

1000 g of Fresh raw cow milk or fresh raw buffalo milk were placed into a cream separator. The cream and skim milk were separated by using cream separator. Then, the cream was placed into a stainless steel pot and heated to boil with continuous agitation to prevent scorching. There was profuse effervescence accompanied by a crackling sound in the early stages of boiling which decreased as the moisture evaporated. When all the moisture had been removed, the temperature of the liquid mass was controlled. The end point was indicated by the appearance of a second effervescence, which was much finer than the first, together with the browning of the curd particles. At this stage, the characteristic ghee flavor was developed.

The final temperature of heating ranged from 110°C to 120°C. After cooling and sedimentation, the ghee was filtered through a muslin cloth to remove the sediment known as "ghee residue" which consisted mostly of burnt co-precipitates. The product acquired the characteristics granular texture on cooling and was placed in sterilized glass bottles and stored at room temperature.

Preparation of Ghee from Creamy Butter

100 g of Creamery butter was placed in a stainless steel pot and heated to about 110°C to 120° with continuous stirring to evaporate the moisture. When all the moisture had been

removed, further heating was avoided by removing the pot from the fire. After the residue had settled down on cooling, the clear fat was filtered through a muslin cloth.

The product acquired the characteristics granular texture on cooling and was placed in sterilized glass bottles and stored at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

Butter was prepared from cream separated from milk samples by using cream separator. The yield percentages of cream and skim milk from different milk samples are shown in Table 1. In traditional method, pasteurized cream was stored at room temperature to acidify automatically. After that, the cream was churned and washed with water. Finally, the prepared butter was packed in a suitable container and stored in the refrigerator. The yield percentages of butter prepared by natural souring are shown in Table 2. It was found that yield percentage of butter prepared from buffalo milk cream is higher than that of butter prepared from cow milk cream.

Butter was also prepared by using mother culture. The effect of amount of mother culture for the required pH of pasteurized milk cream during 16 hr at 21°C was studied by using different amount of mother culture such as 4 g, 5 g, 6 g, 7 g, 8 g, 9 g and 10 g. The results are recorded in Table 3 and 4. After fermentation time of 16 hr, the cream was churned and washed with water. Finally, the prepared cultured butter was removed, packed and stored in the refrigerator. The yield percentages of prepared cultured butters are shown in Table 5. Physical and chemical characteristics of prepared butters were determined and the results are shown in Table 6. It was found that the prepared cultured butters have sweet butter smell and their yield percentages are higher than that of butters prepared by natural souring. Moreover, the fermentation time for ripening of cream by using mother culture is 16 hr but the fermentation time for ripening of cream by natural souring is at least 48 hr. The acidity of prepared butter was determined after each 5 day period. It was found that the acidity was increased sharply after 45 days of storage period. The results are shown in Table 7. Ghee was prepared from milk cream and creamery butter. Yield percentages of ghee are recorded in Table 8. It was found that yield percentage of ghee prepared from creamery butter is higher than that of ghee prepared from milk cream.

The physical and chemical characteristics of prepared ghee-color, refractive index, moisture content, fat content, iodine value, acid value, saponification value, unsaponifiable matter and peroxide value were determined and the results are recorded in Table 9. The quality of ghee prepared from cow milk cream is the best by the data as shown in Table 9.

Table 1. Yield Percentage of Cream and Skim Milk from Different Milk Samples

No.	Milk Samples	Amount of Milk sample	Amount of Cream		Amount of Skim Milk	
		(g)	Weight (g)	Percentage (%) (w/w)	Weight (g)	Percentage (%) (w/w)
1	Cow Milk (Friesian)	1000	70	7.0	930	93.0
2	Cow Milk (Native Cow)	1000	65	6.5	935	93.5
3	Buffalo Milk (River Breed)	1000	89	8.9	911	91.1
4	Buffalo Milk (Swamp Breed)	1000	86	8.6	914	91.4

Table 2. Yield Percentage of Butter Prepared by Natural Souring

No.	Type of Milk Cream	Amount of Milk Cream	Amount of Butter	Yield Percentage of Butter
		(g)	(g)	(%)(w/w)
1	Cow Milk Cream	100	64.5	64.5
2	Buffalo Milk Cream	100	75.2	75.2

Table 3. Effect of Amount of Mother Culture on Acidity and pH of Pasteurized Cow Milk Cream

Weight of Pasteurized Cow Milk Cream = 100 g
 Fermentation Time = 16 h
 Temperature = 21°C

No.	Amount of Mother Culture	Acidity	pH
	(g)	(%)(v/w)	
1	4	1.65	5.4
2	5	1.95	4.9
3	*6	2.175	4.7
4	7	2.25	4.6
5	8	2.3	4.5
6	9	2.75	4.3
7	10	3.12	4.1

* Suitable Amount of Mother Culture = 6 g

Table 4. Effect of Amount of Mother Culture on Acidity and pH of Pasteurized Buffalo Milk Cream

Weight of Pasteurized Buffalo Milk Cream = 100 g
 Fermentation Time = 16 h
 Temperature = 21°C

No.	Amount of Mother Culture	Acidity	pH
	(g)	(%)(v/w)	
1	4	0.525	6.4
2	5	0.9	5.9
3	6	1.26	5.6
4	7	1.58	5.4
5	8	1.93	4.9
6	* 9	2.17	4.7
7	10	2.31	4.6

* Suitable amount of mother culture = 9 g

Table 5. Yield Percentage of Prepared Cultured Butter

No.	Type of Milk Cream	Amount of Milk Cream	Amount of Cultured Butter	Yield Percentage of Cultured Butter
		(g)	(g)	(%)(w/w)
1	Cow Milk Cream	100	68.2	68.2
2	Buffalo Milk Cream	100	80.4	80.4

Table 6. Physical and Chemical Characteristics of Butter

No.	Physical Characteristics	Butter				Literature
		B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄	
1	Color	Pale Yellow	White	Pale Yellow	White	
2	Odor	-	-	Sweet Butter odor	Sweet Butter odor	
3	Refractive Index	1.465	1.458	1.46	1.458	
Chemical Characteristics						
4	Moisture Content (%) (w/w)	13	12	12	12	12-16%
5	Fat Content (%) (w/w)	81	83	82	83	80-85%
6	Protein Content (%) (w/w)	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.2-0.5%
7	pH	5.8	5.7	5.8	5.8	-
8	Acidity (%) (v/w)	0.32	0.31	0.32	0.33	-

B₁ = Butter Prepared from Cow Milk Cream by Natural SouringB₂ = Butter Prepared from Buffalo Milk Cream by Natural SouringB₃ = Cultured Butter Prepared from Cow Milk CreamB₄ = Cultured Butter Prepared from Buffalo Milk Cream

Table 7. Effect of Storage Time on Acidity of Prepared Butter

No.	Storage Period (Day)	Acidity (%) (v/w)
1	5	0.32
2	10	0.32
3	15	0.34
4	20	0.34
5	25	0.34
6	30	0.35
7	35	0.36
8	40	0.36
9	45	0.38
10	50	0.52

Table 8. Yield Percentage of Ghee produced from Milk Cream and Creamery Butter

Weight of Milk Cream = 100 g

Weight of Creamery Butter = 100 g

No.	Raw Material	Amount of Ghee	
		Weight(g)	Percentage (%) (w/w)
1	Milk Cream	50	50
2	Creamery Butter	80	80

Table 9. Characteristics of Ghee

Items	Ghee (I)	Ghee (II)	Ghee (III)	Ghee (IV)	** Literature
Moisture Content (%) (w/w)	0.27	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.1 - 0.3
Fat Content (%) (w/w)	99.4	99.5	99.5	99.6	99.5 - 99.8
Acid Value	0.43	0.6	0.75	0.79	-
Saponification Value	227.5	235.34	233.54	237.28	221 - 223
Unsaponifiable matter (%) (w/w)	0.53	0.33	0.36	0.31	-
Iodine Value	38.28	35.33	33.16	30.79	26 - 38
Peroxide Value	1.5	1.7	2.1	2.3	1.5 - 3.5
Refractive Index	1.4555	1.4558	1.4548	1.4552	1.4530 - 1.4560

Ghee (I) = Ghee Prepared from Cow Milk Cream

Ghee (II) = Ghee Prepared from Buffalo Milk Cream

Ghee (III) = Ghee Prepared from Cow Creamery Butter

Ghee (IV) = Ghee Prepared from Buffalo Creamery Butter

Conclusion

In the preparation of butter, two methods were used. 2% of sample culture was used to prepare mother culture. 6% of mother culture is suitable to ripen cow milk cream at 21°C within 16 hr. 9% of mother culture is suitable to ripen buffalo milk cream at 21°C within 16 hr. The preparation of cultured butter by using mother culture took fermentation time 16 hr but butter prepared by natural souring took fermentation time of about 48 hr. Yield percentage of cultured butter is higher than that of butter prepared by natural souring.

In the section for preparation of ghee, ghee was prepared from milk cream and creamery butter. It was concluded that the quality of ghee prepared from cow milk cream is the best among these samples.

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Online Materials

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